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Effects of Simulation Games and Rote Learning Strategies on Performance in Numeracy Concept among Lower Basic Pupils in Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the effect of simulation games and Rote Learning Instructional Strategies on Performance among Numeracy pupils in Lower Basic Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Two objectives corresponding research questions and hypotheses, respectively guided the study. Quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of 423,036 (Male 253,821 and Female 169,215) lower basic class II pupils during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kaduna State. A sample of 248 (male, 166 and Female, 82) pupils were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. Numeracy Performance Test (NPT) was used to collect data for the study. Reliability index of 0.697 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Mean and Standard Deviations was used to analyse the research questions. sample-paired and independent t-test statistical tools were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed that pupils taught the concept numeracy using simulation Games had higher performance than those exposed to lecture method. However, both simulation games and rote learning can be used to teach numeracy as they improved performance than the Conventional Strategy. The study recommended that; Simulation games strategy should be used by teachers of numeracy since performance improved after treatment and Rote learning strategy should be used by teachers of numeracy since performance improved after treatment.

Keywords: Simulation Games, Rote learning Strategies, Performance and Numeracy.

Introduction

Numeracy is one of the core subjects taught at the Lower Basic School, through which the child is exposed to good knowledge of numbers, basic operations, fractions to mention but a few. Pupils' intellectual growth greatly benefits from numeracy education, especially in basic schools. However, many pupils need help, understanding and retaining numerical concepts, which can hinder their overall performance and achievement. Educators and researchers have recently explored various instructional strategies to enhance pupils' learning experiences and outcomes in Numeracy. Most nations developed, because of the role played by teachers through their teaching activities. Hence, teaching must be done so pupils perceive, understand, and retain what has been taught to record higher scores of meaningful applications of knowledge in different situations. Teachers should be equipped with the latest techniques, strategies, systematic processes and procedures to achieve the stated aims and objectives, for obtaining sustainable learning outcomes, (Guga, 2019).

Simulation games have emerged as a promising tool in Numeracy education. These games provide pupils with interactive and engaging learning environments that simulate real-world mathematical scenarios. Pupils can enhance their problem-solving abilities and better comprehend mathematical ideas by actively engaging in the game's problem-solving activities. Moreover, simulation games offer opportunities for immediate feedback, which can help pupils identify and correct their mistakes, leading to enhanced learning and performance, (Ajai 2020). On the other hand, Rote Learning Strategy has been traditionally employed in Numeracy education. Rote Learning involves the teacher deploying a large amount of information to learners, emphasizing memorization and repetition of mathematical facts, formulas, and procedures. While this approach can result in quick recall of information, more is needed to promote deep understanding and conceptual mastery. However, Iwuji 2012 argued that, proponents of Rote Learning argue that it can be effectively applicable in certain contexts, particularly for learning procedural knowledge and basic mathematical facts, (Iwuji, 2012).

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The theoretical framework on which this study was built upon is the theory of constructivism. The significance of educational theory is paramount, serving as the guiding framework or blueprint to be interpreted and implemented for effective teaching. This study's foundational theories are rooted in constructivism and constructive controversy. Key proponents of these theories whose models were applied include John Dewey, Jean Piaget, Jerome Bruner, and Vygotsky, who are often regarded as philosophical pioneers in this approach. Fundamentally, constructivism is a theory grounded in empirical observation and scientific study that explains how individuals learn. It posits that, people construct their knowledge and comprehension of the world by actively engaging with experiences and reflecting upon them. The theory is about people using their experiences and cognitive abilities to study problems and learn skills or concepts. Learners use their senses to construct new ideas actively using existing knowledge and skills. Constructivism is a major learning theory and is particularly applicable to the learning of Mathematics. It is a theory grounded in empirical observation and practical application.

Statement of the Research Problem

Over time, the researchers, being teachers, observed persistent failure in internal and placement examinations in the basic schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. As 2021/2022 Session recorded 45% failure in Numeracy placement Examination. Then 2022/2023 Session recorded greater failure with 38%. This could result from poor selection of instructional strategies, poor utilization of selected strategies, inadequate instructional materials, and teachers' poor attitude towards teaching. Numeracy, among many of these, tends to influence pupils' performance among Lower Basic Schools. There are many teaching strategies employed in teaching lower basic Numeracy. Teachers are anticipated to use a variety of instructional approaches to foster academic success among lower-basic school pupils. An effective system in the contemporary educational landscape should facilitate extensive social interaction and engagement between teachers and pupils to yield positive outcomes. Creating a supportive, open, and interactive environment for pupils is essential. Such an environment encourages knowledge discovery, enhancing retention and elevating academic performance, particularly in Numeracy among lower-level pupils. (Karan, 2017). The findings of this study hold significance for curriculum developers, Federal Ministry of Education, textbook authors, Numeracy teachers, Numeracy pupils, and researchers in the field.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effects of simulation games and rote learning strategies on numeracy performance and retention among lower basic pupils in Kaduna state Nigeria. While two specific objectives were to:

1. determine the performance of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.
2. examine the performance of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. what is the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria?
2. what is the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated to and tested in the study:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted a Quasi-experimental research design, which employed two experimental groups and one control group with intact classes. All groups underwent a pre-test to assess the pupils' entry capacity. The first experimental group (EG1) received instruction in Numeracy using the Simulation-Games strategy, and the second experimental group (EG2) was taught Numeracy through Rote Learning. In contrast, the control group (CG) received conventional instruction in Numeracy.

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Following a six-week treatment period, a post-test was administered to evaluate the effectiveness of the Simulation-Games and Rote Learning strategies on pupils' performance in lower basic Numeracy schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. This approach aligns with Aliyu (2016), as quasi-experimental design allows for investigating cause-effect relationships between independent and dependent variables.

The study population comprised four hundred and twenty-three thousand and thirty-six 423,036 (Male 253,821 and Female 169,215) Numeracy pupils from all Lower Basic Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The sample size for the study comprised two hundred and forty eight (248) (male, 166 and Female, 82) basic two Numeracy pupils from the intact classes of the sampled Lower Basic Schools. This replicated with Aliyu (2016), who recommended that, the sample size be at least 30 and less than 500 for experimental research. A purposive sampling technique was adopted to select the three Lower Basic Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria, based on a similar Curriculum as the Federal Ministry of Education prescribed. A simple random sampling technique was however, used to assign experimental group one group (EG₁), which was taught Numeracy using simulation games, experimental group two (EG₂), which was taught Numeracy through Rote learning strategy then control group (CG) which was taught using Conventional Strategy.

The instrument Numeracy Performance Test (NPT)" developed by the researcher was based on the content of lower basic two, which included the following topics: identification of numbers 1-50, Addition of whole numbers, subtraction, division, multiplication, and Introduction to fractions. NPT comprises thirty (30) objective questions with four multiple-choice item options A-D each, which carried equal marks of two (2) marks and was rewarded for each correct answer and zero (0) effects for a wrong answer, making sixty (60) marks).

The treatment was administered by the researcher (self) and the whole exercise lasted for six weeks (6). In the experiment, Experimental Group 1 (EG1) received instruction through the Simulation-Games Strategy, Experimental Group 2 (EG2) was taught using the Rote Learning strategy, and the Control Group (CG) was instructed using the Conventional Strategy. Subsequently, a post-test was immediately conducted for all the groups using the data collection instrument (NPT). The scores obtained from this administration were used as post-test performance scores for the study. Following the post-test, the instrument was re-administered for the retention test; one week after the experiment (treatment). This is in order to determine the ability of the pupils to retain, recall and reproduce previously learnt content.

The mean scores and standard deviation obtained from the scores of pre-test, post-test and post-post-test, as well as t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance were used to test the three null hypotheses. The null hypotheses were rejected when t-calculated values were greater than the t-critical values, while the null hypotheses were accepted when t-calculated values were equal to or less than t-critical values.

Presentation of Results

To address the research questions posed in this study, the collected data were subjected to analysis using mean and standard deviation, as outlined below:

Research Question One:

What is the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria?

To address this research question, the data obtained from the post-test were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. A summary of the analysis was presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Post-test Performance of Pupils taught Numeracy using Simulation Games Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Method

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	Decision
Simulation Games	52	24.96	2.80	14.79	Significant
Conventional	52	10.17	2.13		

Source: (Field survey, 2023)

Table 1 above, revealed the effect of Simulation Game Strategy on the performance of pupils as compared to conventional strategy. Meanwhile the table shows that the performance of those taught using Simulation Game Strategy had far better with mean score 24.96 as against that of pupils taught using conventional strategy with the mean score of 10.17 with

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corresponding standard deviation of 2.80 and 2.13 respectively, which indicates that the pupils mean difference is 14.97. This implies that pupils' performance at various strategies have varied from one another.

Research Question Two:

What is the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria?

To address this research question, the data collected from the post-test were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The summary of the analysis was presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Post-test of Performance of Pupils taught Numeracy using Rote Learning Strategy and those Taught using Conventional method

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	Decision
Rote Learning	72	24.96	2.30	14.10	Significant
Conventional	72	10.56	1.87		

Source: (Field survey, 2023)

Table 2 showed the Performance mean score of pupils taught Numeracy using Rote Learning was 24.66 and for pupils taught with Conventional method had a mean of 10.56 with a mean difference of 14.10 was obtained. This indicated that Rote Learning Strategy is also effective strategy for teaching Numeracy to pupils in lower-basic schools.

Null Hypothesis One:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of independent t-test analysis on performances of pupils taught Numeracy using Simulation Games Strategy and those taught using the Conventional Method

Groups	Mean	SD	N	t-cal.	Sig.	Decision
Simulation Games	24.96	2.80	52	11.23	0.00	Rejected
Conventional	10.17	2.13	52			

Source: (Field survey, 2023)

Table 3 showed a significant difference in the performances of pupils taught Numeracy using Simulation-Games Strategy and those exposed to conventional strategy in Lower Basic Schools. The result revealed t-cal. of 11.23 with a p-value of 0.00. The null hypothesis was rejected because the p-value of 0.00 is less than 0.05 level of significant. By implication, there was a difference of 14.79 between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using simulation Games strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method.

Null Hypothesis Two:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching method in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Table 4: Summary of independent t-test analysis on performance scores of pupils taught Numeracy using Rote Learning strategy and those taught with Conventional Method

Groups	Mean	SD	N	t-cal.	Sig.	Decision
Rote Learning	24.66	2.30	72	10.12	0.00	Rejected
Conventional	10.56	1.87	72			

Source: (Field survey, 2023)

Table 4 indicated a significant difference in the performance scores of pupils taught Numeracy using Rote Learning strategy and those taught using Conventional Method in Lower Basic Schools. The result shows a t-cal. of 10.12 with a p-value of 0.00. The null hypothesis was rejected since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the 0.05 significance level. This

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implied Rote Learning Strategy effectively enhanced the learning of Numeracy at the lower basic level in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of study revealed that pupils taught numeracy using simulation games performed better than those taught using conventional method. Therefore, simulation games are effective in teaching pupils numeracy in lower basic schools because there was a significant difference between the Performance of pupils taught Numeracy using simulation games and those taught using Conventional strategies P -value=.000. As a result, the hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference between the Performance of pupils taught Numeracy using simulation games and those taught operating conventional method in lower basic schools in Kaduna state, Nigeria was rejected. The outcomes of this study aligned with previous research findings on the positive impact of Simulation Games on pupils' Performance. This alignment was consistent with the results of Chukwu (2017), who discovered that employing local games in teaching subtraction operations improved pupils' Performance more effectively than conventional lecture methods. Similarly, Ezewi (2019) demonstrated that learners taught with games-based learning strategies outperformed those taught using conventional methods. Ajia (2020) further supported these findings by revealing that students exposed to games and simulations achieved higher geometry performance than those who were not.

The second finding of study revealed that pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning strategy performed better than those taught using the Conventional Method. Therefore, Rote learning was effective in teaching pupils numeracy in lower basic schools because there was a significant difference between the Performance of pupils taught numeracy using Rote learning and those taught using Conventional Method P -value=.000. As a result, the hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference between the Performance of pupils taught Numeracy using Rote learning strategy and those taught operating Conventional Method in lower basic schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria was rejected. This finding aligned with the findings of earlier studies. For example, Christian (2016) observed that pupils in the Mathematical Rote learning strategy group outperformed those in the control group in Mathematics. Additionally, Aladejana (2013) reported that Rote Learning enhances pupils' capacity to recall basic facts rapidly and contributes to developing foundational knowledge in a subject. Instances of rote learning encompass memorizing multiplication tables or the periodic table of elements.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings and recommendations the study concluded that, simulation games and rote learning strategies improves the teaching and learning of numeracy among lower-basic school pupils in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Simulation games strategy should be used by teachers of numeracy since performance improved after treatment.
2. Rote learning strategy should be used by teachers of numeracy since performance improved after treatment.

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